

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

R.A.P

Best
AWARD

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Muhammadiyev Shohboz Bo`ron o`g`li

MAMLAKATIMIZNING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI TA'MINLASH UCHUN OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARI

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2023/AVGUST

